

DIASPORIC MEDIA: MOLDOVAN EMIGRATED CITIZENS AND CIVIC ACTIVISM

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The newspapers and magazines published abroad, founded by emigrated Moldovan citizens, bring additional value to the media of the Republic of Moldova, as a source of information and documentation on the realities of the host countries and situation of emigrated people. This phenomenon represents another aspect of the socio-cultural process that is currently happening abroad, with different characteristics at the various stages of the process of integration of Moldovan emigrated citizens.

The purpose of our research is to analyze the appearance and evolution of newspapers and magazines published abroad by Moldovan emigrants, their specificity and typology, the ways of reflecting the situation of migrants, in an attempt to become a bridge between the communities of the host country and the country of origin.

Keywords: migration, diaspora, diasporic media, moldovan migrants, transnational communication, civic activism.

PRESA DIN DIASPORĂ: CETĂȚENII MOLDOVENI EMIGRAȚI ȘI ACTIVISMUL CIVIC

Ziarele și revistele publicate peste hotare, fondate de cetățenii moldoveni emigrați, aduc o valoare în plus mass-mediei din Republica Moldova, ca sursă de informare și de documentare privind realitățile din țările-gazdă și situația celor emigrați. Acest fenomen reprezintă un aspect specific al unor procese socio-culturale care se desfășoară în prezent peste hotare, cu diferite caracteristici la diverse etape ale procesului de integrare a cetățenilor moldoveni emigrați.

Scopul cercetării noastre este de a analiza apariția și evoluția unor ziare și reviste publicate în străinătate de cetățenii moldoveni emigrați, specificul și tipologia lor, modalitățile de reflectare a situației migranților, în încercarea lor de a deveni o punte de legătură între comunitățile formate în țara gazdă, dar și cu țara de origine.

Cuvinte-cheie: migrație, diaspora, mass-media diasporei, migranți moldoveni, comunicare transnațională, activism civic.

LES MÉDIAS DE LA DIASPORA: CITOYENS MOLDAVES ÉMIGRÉS ET ACTIVISME CIVIQUE

Les journaux et magazines publiés à l'étranger, fondés par des citoyens moldaves émigrés, apportent une valeur supplémentaire aux médias de la République de Moldova, en tant que source d'information et de documentation sur les

réalités des pays d'accueil, ainsi que sur la situation des personnes émigrées. Ce phénomène représente un autre aspect du processus socioculturel qui se déroule actuellement à l'étranger, avec des caractéristiques différentes aux différentes étapes du processus d'intégration des citoyens moldaves émigrés.

Le but de notre recherche est d'analyser l'apparition et l'évolution des journaux et magazines publiés à l'étranger par les citoyens moldaves émigrés, leur spécificité et typologie, les manières de refléter la situation des migrants, dans leur tentative de devenir un pont entre les communautés, dans le pays d'accueil, mais aussi avec le pays d'origine.

***Mots-clés:** migration, diaspora, médias diasporiques, migrants moldaves, communication transnationale, activisme civique.*

МЕДИА ДИАСПОРЫ: МОЛДАВСКИЕ ЭМИГРАНТЫ И ГРАЖДАНСКИЙ АКТИВИЗМ

Издаваемые за границей газеты и журналы, основанные эмигрантами из Молдовы, придают дополнительную ценность средств массовой информации Республики Молдова, как источник информации и документации о реалиях принимающих стран, а также о положении эмигрантов. Этот феномен представляет собой еще один аспект социокультурного процесса, который в настоящее время происходит за границей, с разными характеристиками на разных этапах процесса интеграции молдавских эмигрировавших граждан.

Целью нашего исследования является анализ появления и эволюции газет и журналов, изданы за границей молдавскими эмигрантами, их специфика и типология, способы отражения положения мигрантов, в их попытке стать мостом между сообществами, сформированными в принимающей стране, а также со страной происхождения.

***Ключевые слова:** миграция, diaspora, медиа diasпоры, молдавские мигранты, транснациональная коммуникация, гражданский активизм.*

Introduction

The migration phenomenon is traditionally accompanied by the generation of adjacent phenomena. It is natural that among these is the phenomenon of the media. The media helps migrants in the effort to represent themselves, to set up networks, to recover the communication deficit. In the last two decades, there are more attempts to create communication (online) spaces for migrant communities, and the new media have a special role. The phenomenon of globalization and the evolution of information technologies have accelerated this process. Researchers pointed out the terms as Diasporic media and Diaspora journalism, considering not only TV, radio or print media (newspapers, magazines, etc.), but also the portals and the audio / video / photo platforms for migrants. Some authors insist on considering the media of diaspora as a platform for communication

in the host country („a platform for self-expression”), for cultural representation, for combating the stereotypes and clichés. [7, p. 1] They consider them spaces of inclusion, political participation and civic activism. [5, p. 21] Also, Diasporic media „reinforce identities and sense of belonging”, „have significant implications for participating (or not) in European societies and transnational communities”. [3, p. 481] The researchers emphasize the importance of the media for strengthening diaspora communities, in the sense that they provide open spaces, as an alternative, for the discourses of emigrants. For several reasons, these media are rarely used. However, these media complement other media in the country of origin and in the country of migration. [5] According to a definition of the Diasporic media, these „are produced by and for migrants and deal with issues that are of specific interest to the members of diasporic communities”. [1, p. 97] The researches have shown

that Diasporic media tend to go further, beyond borders - to transnational communication. These trends are evident in most migrant communities in many countries. Migrants tend to communicate not only with members of their community, but also with other conationals from other cities, countries, or from the country of origin. Among the aspects that need to be taken into account can be considered the „complexity of connections and networks within the diaspora and beyond”, „the complex relation between identity and the media” – „that indicates how media become significant agents for diaspora, identity and community”. [4]

Dinamics of diasporic media

The evolution of newspapers and magazines founded by Moldovan emigrated citizens, in general, are part of the Romanian socio-cultural context existing in the migration countries. The aim of our research is to analyze the appearance and evolution of newspapers and magazines published abroad by Moldovan emigrants, the issues addressed, their specificity and typology, their role in the communities formed in the host country, but also the connections with the country of origin. In this research, the main criteria taken into account were chronological criteria (stages of evolution), geographical (country and place of residence), editorial team (founding members), languages (were published only texts in Romanian or in other languages), topics addressed, periodicity of editorial appearances, etc.

Sometimes, one of the stages was the publication of parish bulletins, before the creation of editorial teams with the purpose to publish newspapers or magazines. In some communities, for example in Canada, have been published brochures (as the authors called them), available online, with a certain periodicity (three editions have already appeared: 2015-2016, 2016-2017 and 2017-2018). Their purpose

is to publish useful and interesting information for the community - from the Republic of Moldova and from the country of residence, and also to promote remarkable integration stories, cultural events, educational activities with children, etc.

We must note the constant interest of the Moldovan media in what is happening in the diaspora. As the „Mediacritica” portal writes, the issue of migration becomes much more than a news topic and the national press has an important role in building bridges between the emigrants and the country of origin. But there are also risk factors - especially in election campaigns. Subjects related to the diaspora are exploited by political parties according to their own interests, trying to obtain dividends and involving the diaspora in various political intrigues. In such cases, we are talking about a certain illusion of values and promotion of false values, in the country of origin and in the host country. Another risk factor is the drastic decrease of the number of those who read the written press in the Republic of Moldova. According to a study, recently published, in the Republic of Moldova the print media is read less than in other countries - only 1 out of 3 Moldovan citizens regularly read the printed newspapers and only 1 out of 10 - local magazines.

The evolution of publications abroad in Romanian language has a long, complex history, with different purposes and topics, influenced, for the most part, by the historical context. The great historical events, the social transformations were reflected. Can be indicated in this context the publication of newspapers and magazines by young Romanians who emigrated after the 1848 revolution, including students - in Paris, France („România viitoare”, „Junimea română”, „Buciumul”, „Opiniunea”, „Republica română”, etc.), in Brussels, Belgium („L'Étoile du Danube”), in Turkey („Conservatorul”). [8] Some publications from abroad appeared only for a short period (1918-1919), being financially supported by

the Romanian state, in order to promote national ideals. Is relevant the appearance in 1918-1919 of some publications in the Russian space - „Gazeta Transilvaniei și a Bucovinei” (Chelyabinsk), „Vestitorul” (Irkutsk), „Neamul Românesc” (Irkutsk – Vladivostok) etc. Another publication appeared in Moscow in 1917 - „Foaia țăranului”, another publication in St. Petersburg - „L’Entente”. „România Mare” was published in Kiev, Ukraine (later in Paris, France). Two publications have appeared in Europe: in Italy, „Neamul românesc”, and in Germany - the magazine „Orizonturi noi”. [8]

The numerous Bessarabian periodicals was published abroad – in France, Belgium, Germany, Russia and Ukraine. [2] They were based on „enthusiastic starts” of the authors and did not receive any support from the country of origin.

A specific stage in the history of the Romanian press abroad is the Romanian exile - with many titles of newspaper and magazine, including the magazine „Agora” (USA), with the collaboration of the Romanian writer Paul Goma. The researcher Mihaela Albu referred to this magazine and also to several aspects related to the literature of emigration and exile – pointing out the need of some emigrants to continue the journalistic and literary activity, the need to maintain the national language and identity, etc. (a useful source of documentation about the evolution of the Romanian language media abroad, after the World War II, is Florin Manolescu’s book, „Encyclopedia of the Romanian Exile (1945-1989)”, as well as the website of the Institute for the Investigation of the Crimes of Communism and Romanian Exile).

Starting with the 2000s, the list of Romanian publications abroad has been diversified. The theme of exile has been abandoned. Over the years, issues related to the mass emigration of Romanian citizens have prevailed. Currently, several sources provide information on Romanian language publications abroad (in about 15 countries).

The project Migrants Diaspora Initiative for Media Enterprise and PRO-DIASPORA Magazine

In the late 2000s, one of the first magazines published at the initiative of Moldovan emigrants was „Pro-diaspora”, an ambitious project dedicated to diaspora. The first issue of the magazine appeared on December 1, 2009, within the project „Migrants Diaspora Initiative for Media Enterprise (Migrants DIME)”. The project was carried out in partnership with the Association of Independent Press of the Republic of Moldova and 12 (later the number increased to 22) associations of Moldovan citizens established abroad (UK, Italy, Austria, Spain, Portugal, Belgium, France). „The first magazine about and for migrants from the Republic of Moldova”, as it was called by the authors, appeared in Chisinau, in 2009-2011, a circulation of 10.000 copies, distributed free of charge in 15 European countries.

The magazine included several sections: Remittances, Politics, Success Story, The „Wounds” of Migration, A Village Portrait, Civic Spirit, The Difficulties of Migration, Charity, etc. The editorial team, initially led by the editor-in-chief Dumitru Lazur (later Dumitru Baci) consisted of reporters established in 5 countries: Diana Lungu (Republic of Moldova), Olesca Tanașciuc (Portugal), Victor Druță, Larisa Olărescu, Larisa Pojoga, Ludmila Cearcă (Italy), Marcel Macarie (Spain), Violeta Grițcan (France), Nadea Hornet (Czech Republic). The writers Eugenia Bulat and Iurie Bojoncă (Venice, Italy) collaborated with this magazine. The authors of the magazine planned to print, in addition, a newspaper – „Gazeta Pro-diaspora” - an initiative that remained at the project stage.

The first issue of the newspaper „Gazeta Basarabiei”, called by the authors „the newspaper of Moldovan migrants”, appeared in April 2009. The publication aims to approach several topics: the life of Moldovan communities abroad, socio-economic and political events in Moldova and from the host

countries of Moldovan citizens, legislative news on migration, etc. The director of the newspaper is Olga Coptu, former head of the Diaspora Relations Bureau, of the Government of Chisinau. Olga Coptu was the candidate of the Democratic Party of Moldova, for the 50th Circumscription - Western Europe - in the parliamentary elections of February 24, 2019. The editor-in-chief of the publication is Jana Reniță, established in Italy. The editorial team includes Moldovan citizens from several countries: Dorin Dușciac (France), Oleseș Tanașciuc (Portugal), Aliona Purci (Italy), Svetlana Lisagor Vergis (Greece). For several years, the newspaper was distributed free of charge in more than 12 cities in Italy and in the capitals of the other three countries. The publication has been registered at the Ministry of Justice since 2012. Over the past 11 years, many stories of migrants from the Republic of Moldova have been reflected, events organized in the diaspora, participation in elections in the country of origin or migration, changes in the legislative framework, bilateral political agreements, etc. „Gazeta Basarabiei” is a Romanian language publication, but sometimes were also included texts in Italian. In August 2014, the editorial team of „Gazeta Basarabiei” organized in Chisinau an international conference entitled „Republic of Moldova 2020: The contribution of the diaspora to the development of the country of origin”. The event was attended by representatives of the diaspora, and also by academic environment in Chisinau, politicians and experts in the field.

In 2010 in the Italian city of Brescia was created the Association for social promotion Moldbrixia. After a year of activity, in March 2011 the first issue of the magazine „Moldbrixia news” was published. President of the association and director of the magazine is the journalist and writer Lilia Bicec, the author of the books „Unread Testament”, „Boome-

rang” and „Camp 33”, published in Chisinau by Cartier. The books were translated into Italian and published in Italy. In the magazine, the texts are published in Romanian and Italian, and the editorial team includes Moldovan and Italian citizens. The journal is available online: 16 issues, published in 2011-2017, in part thanks to the support of the International Organization for Migration. In 2011, in the first year of publication, 6 issues appeared. In 2012-2013 the magazine appeared twice a year, and until 2017 - once a year. In the first issue of the magazine, in the editorial entitled „Integration is not a chimera”, Lilia Bicec noted the need to cover the information gap affecting emigrants, to create an effective information network to keep Moldovan emigrants up to date with legislative changes, news from diplomatic missions, cultural or other events organized by the community of Brescia.

Magazines dedicated to children: „Pro Diaspora Kids” and „Pici Voinici” (*fr.* „Enfants Braves”)

In 2011, one of the most beautiful and well-made children’s magazines appeared. In excellent graphic conditions, with a content addressed to both emigrant children and parents. The first issue of „Pro Diaspora Kids” magazine, Portugal, appeared in 2011 thanks to a grant from International Organization for Migration. In the period 2011-2013 the magazine appeared once a year, on the International Children’s Day. In 2013, the magazine received financial support from the Swedish International Development Cooperation Agency, whose representatives praised the magazine as a very interesting project, supporting the idea of distributing the magazine not only in Portugal but also in other European countries. The initiative was saluted by representatives of associations from France, Italy, Ireland and the United Kingdom. In 2014, the magazine was published with the financial support of the Honorary Consul of the Republic

of Moldova in Portugal. In 2015-2016, the magazine appeared with the support of Diaspora Relations Bureau and Organization for Migration, twice a year (summer - Children's Day and winter – Christmas Day). Until 2017, the magazine was published as a voluntary publication (and distributed free of charge), without being officially registered in the Republic of Moldova or Portugal. In the absence of funding sources, in 2017 Oleseă Tanașciuc decided to propose the magazines for sale, in order to be able to edit the next issue. Therefore the magazine was registered in Portugal. But only 25 percent was sold, insufficient to cover printing costs. In the summer of 2018, on Children's Day, was published another issue of the magazine.

The magazine „Pro Diaspora Kids” was called by its authors „the first magazine for Moldovan children in Europe”. The team collaborated with the „Youth Media Center”, from Republic of Moldova, and „Moldbrixia” Association, from Italy. One of the issues of the magazine (no. 1 from 2016), dedicated to the International Children's Day, has a rich content, structured in four sections, dedicated to the 4 countries of residence of Moldovan citizens. Several topics are included in the chapters: Rights and Opportunities (family allowance in Portugal, Italy and Ireland), Statistical Data on Moldovan migrants in Portugal, the French School System and the schooling of foreign students, Specialist Advice (identity of Moldovans abroad), Useful Information (Orthodox parishes in Portugal, Italy and Ireland) etc. One of the news items refers to a monument of the Romanian writer Lucian Blaga (former ambassador to Lisbon), in the city of Estoril, Portugal. In her editorial, the president of the „Pro-Diaspora” Media Association, Oleseă Tanașciuc, notes: „We tend to be a bridge between the diaspora, the homeland and the host state, to intensify communication in the mother tongue with those who are part of a nation with us, to in-

form about useful and interesting things related to children, activities, legislation, opportunities, etc. To promote the traditions, to enjoy the fundamental rights related to the preservation of the national identity - the use of the mother tongue, the access to the religious service in Romanian, the access to information, the participation in the social, economic and cultural life”.

The first issue of the children's magazine „Pici Voinici” (*fr.* „Enfants Braves”, *en.* „Brave children”), Canada, appeared on February 14, 2016, on the birthday of the Romanian writer Grigore Vieru. The editor-in-chief is the writer Liuba Sârbu (Canada), and the editor - the writer Doru Ciocanu (Canada). The plastic artist Lică Sainciuc (Republic of Moldova) is the author of the drawings published in the magazine. The authors are different in most issues of the magazine: „a collaboration between poets and authors who write for children - from Romania, the Republic of Moldova and the diaspora - representing creations of contemporary authors, but also of those who wrote a special page in the history of children's literature”. Among the Bessarabian writers, in the pages of the magazine were published works by Grigore Vieru, Vasile Romanciuc, Constantin Dragomir, Nicolae Dabija, Claudia Partole, Titus Știrbu, Aurel Ciocanu, etc. Among the Romanian writers, were inserted works signed by Nichita Stănescu, Adrian Păunescu, Ana Blandiana, Petre Crăciun and others. Among the classics, were included in the magazine creations by Mihai Eminescu, Ion Creangă, Vasile Alecsandri, George Topârceanu, George Coșbuc and others. Also, were published creations of authors from the diaspora: Liuba Sârbu and Lilian Curevici (Republic of Moldova), Melania Rusu Caragioiu and Eva Halus (Romania), etc. The magazine was originally published six times a year. For now, the publication was stopped, for financial reasons, as the number of subscribers does not cover editing costs.

The connection with migrant literature - „Mămăliga de Varşovia”, Poland (en. „Warsaw bitter maize porridge”)

The magazines published abroad have tangents with the emigration literature, as well as in the case of Moldovan emigrated citizens - the journalistic activity is related to the literary one. An example of this can be the magazine „Mămăliga de Varşovia”, Poland (en. „Warsaw bitter maize porridge”), made by a team coordinated by the writer Teodor Ajder. The first number of the magazine „Warsaw bitter maize porridge” or „Biannual Magazine in Romanian, Polish and English”, as the authors called it, includes - in 261 pages - written articles between November 2014 - June 2015, published, in part, on the blog. The second issue of the magazine appeared in 2016 and had 318 pages. At the beginning of 2018, the third issue of the magazine appeared. In June 2018, the deadline for submitting materials for the next issue expired. The first two issues of the magazine were launched in Poland, but also in Chisinau, at the National Library of the Republic of Moldova. The editorial team includes Teodor Ajder, Claudia Ciobanu, Olga Corochii, Mihai I. Tarță, etc. Authors (journalists, writers, artists, illustrators, photographers) from several countries also collaborated on the first issue: Ghenadie Stanca, Rui Işihara, Ghenadie Popescu, Ramin Mazur, Cristina Burlacu, Vitalie Vovc, Vitalie Sprânceană, Aliona Bereghici, Aju Tutu, Julian Ajder, Mădălina Voicu, Aurelia Zavtoni (over 20 people) etc. An original magazine, which begins with a legend / guide about the specifics of the arrangement / content of the texts, each with a separate graphic symbol, followed by Contents, with specific graphic characters, called by the authors „Mămăliga 2.0”, „Candara”. More than 80 topics were proposed in the first number of the magazine.

The first number covers a wide range of issues related to the situation of emigrants - from the initi-

ative of founding a magazine („as an experiment”), to civic activism and voting (in the host country and of origin); interviews (with the writer Vasile Ernu, with the photographer Ramin Mazur, the illustrator Aliona Bereghici etc.); discrimination; controversies (Teodor Ajder, Warsaw - Vitalie Vovc, Paris); Romanian Book Club in Warsaw, etc. The second issue of the magazine proposed a structure summarized in several sections: Migration, Agora, History, Prose, Chronicles and Recipes. There is a special focus on some aspects related to migration: the names of newborns in the country of migration as a reason for discrimination, feeling like a foreigner in the host country, refugees in Poland and Germany, the odyssey of alienation / estrangement, the immigrant as a child (difficulties related to not speaking the language of the host country), immigrants between statistics and art, about crypto-racism in social networks and the humiliating fear of foreigners, interview with co-founders of the project „Traveling Birds”, short prose by Dragoş Voicu, etc.

In the period 2016-2018, in Chisinau appeared Diaspora Magazine „Moldova de Oriunde” (a publication of Diaspora Relations Bureau), published with the support of Swedish International Development Cooperation Agency, which complemented the efforts of journalists to bring information to the public in Moldova, about communities and associations of Moldovan citizens.

Conclusions

The efforts of the national media to establish an open and constant dialogue with the representatives of the communities of Moldovan citizens abroad, in order to have access to information and to reflect their situation, have become more frequent.

At the same time, for several years the *newspapers and magazines* founded abroad by the migrants tried to build bridges between the country of origin

and the host country, presenting the legislative changes, useful information in different fields (obtaining residence documents or travel to the country of origin), reflection of events (political, social, economic or cultural) organized by migrant communities, civic activism, participation in elections, life stories, etc.

These efforts culminated in 2016, in particular, when a convergence of interests was created between the Moldovan media and the communities of citizens settled abroad. An important role in these developments has been played by the development of communication technologies - today the communication is much faster and less expensive than in the 2000s.

The *newspapers and magazines* appeared abroad, founded by Moldovan emigrated citizens, add value to the national media, as a source of information and documentation on the realities of the countries of residence, the political, socio-economic, cultural situation, situation of emigrants. Also, „as mediators” of new social relations. [6, p. 12]

Newspapers and magazines created by Moldovan citizens abroad are part of the context of the evolution of the Romanian press abroad. However, this is not an isolated phenomenon, broken by the realities of the national press. Beyond the specifics of each one, the media face common difficulties: financial security of the publishing activity, low number of subscriptions, low interest in purchasing print or electronic editions, lack of support from the state. Attempts to publish these newspapers and magazines abroad come from a natural urge to inform the target audience, to communicate and beyond the boundaries of communities established in a migra-

ting city or country - it is the desire to cross borders and to communicate with people settled in other cities, countries, continents.

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